

Catalytic Formation of Methane from Carbon Monoxide and Hydrogen.

Part I.

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Production of methane from carbon monoxide is a very important technical process, and in the Cedford process a mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide in the ratio of 5 to 1 volumes is passed over nickel catalyst at about 300°C resulting in the complete conversion of carbon monoxide into methane. Theoretically three volumes of hydrogen are required for one of carbon monoxide but in actual practice it is found that if the percentage of carbon monoxide in the mixture is kept above 17%, the catalyst is quickly spoilt by carbon deposition due probably to the reaction,

The attainment of the hydrogen-rich gas by partial removal of carbon monoxide from blue water-gas by liquefaction is an operation of considerable expense and the Cedford process is not a commercial success.

Medsforth has recently studied (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1452) the action of various promoters on the velocity of methane formation by nickel catalyst in a gas mixture of carbon monoxide and hydrogen (1 : 5) and finds that the efficiency of the promoters runs parallel with their catalytic dehydrating capacity. He suggests the following mechanism for the reaction :

According to him cerium oxide is the best promoter for this reaction.

In our experiments the chief object was to prepare a catalyst which would retain its activity undiminished in a gas mixture of H_2 and CO in the theoretical ratio of 3 : 1. It was felt that if the poisoning of the catalyst is due to carbon deposition on nickel surface, a nickel surface deposited on carbon itself would have better chance of retaining its activity, for the atoms of carbon produced in reaction (1) might get fixed to particles of carbon which form the support of the nickel catalyst in preference to the atoms of nickel. This expectation was realised in actual experiment and it was found that a sugar-charcoal-nickel catalyst retained its activity for months.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A mixture of concentrated cane-sugar solution and Kahlbaum's nickel acetate was dropped into a strongly heated nickel crucible with a very smooth surface from a separating funnel; the quantity of solution dropped each time should on no account exceed the amount which could swell up and partially carbonise instantaneously. When a considerable quantity of this voluminous and partially carbonised product was obtained, the crucible was heated from all sides, until the catalyst just began to burn of itself. The crucible was then covered with lid and the product further heated from below until the evolution of fumes ceased. The product obtained was finally heated strongly in an asbestos-covered hard glass tube, in absence of air till all gases ceased to come out. To get voluminous active product too much of sugar must be avoided and the surface of the nickel crucible must be very smooth. Before use the catalyst was reduced in a current of purified hydrogen for twenty-four hours at temperatures between 210° and 250° . Carbon monoxide and hydrogen were prepared by the action of sulphuric acid on sodium formate and zinc

respectively, purified in the usual way and stored in a large glass vessel in the ratio of 1 : 3 volumes. The gas mixture was passed over the catalyst at various speeds by forcing water under pressure in the storage vessel and was desiccated on its way. The catalyst material was at the centre of a hard glass tube with asbestos-plugs on either sides, and was heated uniformly in an electric tube furnace, which was maintained at any constant temperature by regulating the current. The out-flow gases were collected from time to time in a Hempel gas burette and analysed in the usual way. The rate of passing of gas was measured by means of a flow-meter. The temperature could be seen from a mercury thermometer placed in contact with the catalyst material. The experimental data are given in Tables I and II, where *S. V.* = space velocity, *i.e.*, c.c.s. of gas per c.c. of catalyst material per minute.

TABLE I.

Catalyst:—Sugar-Charcoal-Nickel (73 : 27). Composition of Outflow Gases.

T° C	S. V.	% CH ₄	% CO ₂	% CO	% H ₂
300	0.23	75	9	0	16
	0.74	62	9.8	0	28
	1.08	53	8.8	0	38
	2.40	33	6.1	9.7	51.3
335	1.55	68	9.4	0	22.5
	1.76	65	9.5	0.7	24.7
355-360	1.69	65.7	7	0	27.4
	3.54	54.0	9.5	0	36.0
	3.69	50.0	10.5	0.8	39.0
405	4.32	63	9	0	28

TABLE II.

*Catalyst: Sugar-charcoal-Nickel-Ceria*¹

T ^o C	S.V.	% OH ₂	% CO ₂	% CO	% H ₂
300	2.6	80	4.2	12.3	54
355	2.1	67.5	8.4	0	23.6
	3.4	65.4	5.9	0	25.3
	4.4	57.4	8.4	0	34

It was noticed that traces of nickel got deposited on the sides of the tube on allowing the sugar charcoal catalyst to cool in an atmosphere of the reaction mixture from a temperature of 500.^o But in the case of ceria as a promoter of the catalyst, such a deposit appeared on cooling from 300.^o This phenomenon did not occur when the catalyst was cooled in a current of hydrogen.

It will be noticed from Table I that for every temperature there is a critical space velocity beyond which CO appeared in the outflow gases. This critical velocity increases considerably as the temperature of the reaction increases. Thus at 300.^o this critical space velocity is about 1.3, at 335.^o it is 1.7, at 358.^o 3.6 and at 400.^o it lies above 4.3. With ceria as promoter the efficiency of the catalyst increases but not to the extent found by Medforth with nickel catalyst supported on pumice stone. Thus at about 355.^o, the critical space velocity is 3.5 without ceria, while with ceria it is above 4.4.

Origin of CO₂ in the Outflow Gases.

The experimental data recorded above disclose the drawback that with this particular catalyst a considerable

¹ Sugarcharcoal : Nickel : Cerium nitrate
80 : 27 : 2.3

amount of CO_2 is produced. Carbon dioxide may be produced by either or both of the following reactions :—

The analysis of the incoming and the outflow gases makes it possible to decide which of these reactions is responsible for the production of CO_2 . If 75 vols. of hydrogen and 25 vols. of carbon monoxide give x vols. of CH_4 and y vols. of CO_2 and z vols. of hydrogen then, if reaction (1) alone were to proceed, besides methane formation according to reaction,

the relative volume of $\text{CH}_4 : \text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2$ would be $(25-2y) : y : 75-3(25-2y)$ or $(25-2y) : y : 6y$ (Eq 1). Whereas if reaction (2) were to proceed only, the relative volumes of $\text{CH}_4 : \text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2$ would be as $(25-2y+y)$ or as $25-y : y : 75-3(25-2y)-2y$ or as $25-y : y : 4y$. (Eq. 2)

In the previous tables it will be seen that the ratio of CO_2 to H_2 is never as 1 : 6 indicating that reaction (1) is not taking place at all. The ratio is in some cases approximately 1 : 4. The formation of CO_2 is purely due to reaction (2). In the majority of cases part of the carbon dioxide is produced by reaction (2) but a considerable portion must be produced by some other type of reaction. Perhaps here we are dealing with the reaction,

with water vapour produced in reaction (3). If this reaction were only to proceed then

$$\text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2 :: y : 2y \quad \dots \quad (Eq. 3)$$

From the tables it is at once apparent that reaction (4) alone is not responsible for the production of CO_2 except in the case recorded in Table I for 300° with space velocity of 0.33. In fact in the majority of cases it

is produced partly by reaction (2) and by (4). If y of CO_2 is made of y_2 and y_4 , or if $y = y_2 + y_4$, then

$$x : y : z :: (25 - 2y_2) : y_2 + y_4 : [75 - 3(25 - 2y_2) - 2y_2 + 2y_4]$$

or $4y_2 + 2y_4$.

The ratio $x : y : z$ being known y_2 and y_4 can be calculated. Calculations according to Eq. 4 show that as the space velocity increases, reaction (4) tends to be suppressed until for high space velocities reaction (2) alone becomes responsible for the production of CO_2 .

The equations showing the variation of equilibrium constants with temperature for reactions involved here are given below.

$$\log K_p = \frac{37,600}{4.571T} - 1.75 \log T + .0006T - 3.8$$

$$\log K_p = \frac{57,250}{4.571T} - 3.5 \log T - 4.5$$

$$\log K_p = \frac{47,150}{4.571T} - 3.5 \log T - 2.2$$

and for the reaction (4)

which might be split up into reactions,

and the approximate Nernst equation will be

$$\log K_p = -\frac{18,900}{4.571T} + 1.75 \log T - 0.8$$

It will be noticed that as the temperature increases the formation of carbon dioxide, according to equation (4), is favoured and the quantity of CO in equilibrium with CH₄ according to Eqs. 2 and 3 ceases to be negligible.

Summary.

(1) A sugar-charcoal-nickel catalyst for the reaction, $\text{CO} + 3\text{H}_2 = \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ retains its activity undiminished for months when the ratio of H₂:CO is 3:1 and the critical space velocity below which CO disappears from the outflow gases is quite large.

(2) This catalyst entirely suppresses the reaction $2\text{CO} = \text{C} + \text{CO}_2$ and prevents the deposition of carbon on nickel surface.

(3) Ceria acts as a promoter for this catalyst.

(4) Some amount of CO₂ is generated during the operation which is mainly due to the reaction, $2\text{CO} + 2\text{H}_2 = \text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4$ and partly to the reaction, $\text{C} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{CO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2$

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